

Stable pyrrole-linked bioconjugates through tetrazine-triggered azanorbornadiene fragmentation

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Abstract: We have developed an azanorbornadiene bromovinyl sulfone reagent that allows cysteine-selective bioconjugation. Subsequent reaction with dipyrityl tetrazine led to bond-cleavage and formation of a pyrrole-linked conjugate. The latter involves ligation of the tetrazine to the azanorbornadiene-tagged protein through inverse electron demand Diels–Alder cycloaddition with subsequent double *retro*-Diels–Alder reactions to form a stable pyrrole linkage. The sequence of site-selective bioconjugation followed by bioorthogonal bond-cleavage was efficiently employed for the labelling of three different proteins. This method benefits from easy preparation of these reagents, selectivity for cysteine, and stability after reaction with a commercial tetrazine, which lends it to the routine preparation of protein conjugates for chemical biology studies.

The installation of synthetic modifications, such as fluorescent/affinity probes or cytotoxic drugs into a pre-determined site on a protein, can help us to understand uptake and intracellular trafficking pathways^[1] or enable the specific delivery of payloads to a cancer tissue in the form of antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs).^[2] The chemical introduction of these modifications onto a protein may be achieved through 1) direct chemical modification of proteinogenic amino acids or 2) by genetic encoding of a non-canonical amino acid in the protein sequence followed by chemical ligation.^[3] Of all proteinogenic

amino acids, the sulfhydryl side-chain of cysteine remains the primary choice to achieve site-selectivity because of its enhanced nucleophilicity and low abundance in its reduced form.^[4] Although many cysteine-bioconjugation strategies have been developed,^[5] the thio-Michael addition reaction to a maleimide acceptor is the most popular for reactions directed at cysteine^[6] because it is fast and quantitative at near neutral pH, and because the reagents used are commercially available with a maleimide handle for conjugation.^[6] The use of maleimides is best illustrated in the generation of clinically used ADCs, such as brentuximab vedotin^[7] and ado-trastuzumab emtansine.^[8] However, thiosuccinimide-cysteine-linked bioconjugates quickly degrade *in vivo* by means of a *retro*-Michael reaction, which leads to thiol-exchanged products (e.g., glutathione or the cysteine at position 34 in albumin).^[9] The inherent instability of the thiosuccinimide linkage is a cause for premature drug-loss and thus potential side-toxicity and decreased therapeutic efficacy.^[10] However, through either hydrolysis^[11] or application of stretching force^[12] stable maleimide–thiol adducts can be obtained.

Reactions that allow formation of new bonds under bioorthogonal conditions are of great interest in chemical biology.^[13] Among these, the inverse electron demand Diels–Alder cycloaddition (IEDDA) between tetrazines and olefin dienophiles stands out for its selectivity, fast kinetics and biocompatibility.^[14] More recently, an inverse strategy (in which a specific bond is cleaved instead of formed) has been proposed and applied for the controlled activation of proteins and prodrugs in cells and animals.^[15] The reaction between aza- and oxabenzonorbornadienes with tetrazines to afford isoindoles and isobenzofurans, respectively, (**Scheme 1**) which was reported by Warrenner in the 1970's,^[16] was further developed as a bioorthogonal bond-cleavage reaction, and used for drug activation^[17] and signal amplification in nucleic acid templated detection of microRNA.^[18] This transformation proceeds through a three-step cascade reaction that is initiated by ligation between the strained alkene of the heterobenzonorbornadiene system **A** and a tetrazine by means of an iEDDA reaction (**Scheme 1**). Upon spontaneous double *retro*-Diels–Alder (*rDA*), which leads to simultaneous extrusion of N₂ and of an aromatic pyridazine, the corresponding isoindole or isobenzofuran is formed quantitatively. However, these products are highly unstable due to their high dienic character.

We have recently developed a method for residue-specific dual protein labelling that consists of cysteine-selective thio-Michael addition to 7-azanorbornadiene system **B** followed by bioorthogonal iEDDA labelling of the resulting 7-azanorbornene

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conjugate with fluorogenic tetrazines (**Scheme 2**).^[19] The ability to perform the iEDDA reaction enabled the incorporation of a second label and also avoided collateral rDA of 7-azanorbornene **C**. Here we describe the use of [2.2.1]bicyclic 2-bromovinyl sulfone of type **D** as a reagent for site-selective protein bioconjugation purposes. We hypothesized that the strained bromovinyl sulfone could react with the sulfhydryl side-chain of cysteine in a selective and fast manner to afford **E**. However, and contrary to the 7-azanorbornene analogue **C**, the subsequent reaction of 7-azanorbornadiene **E** with tetrazines would proceed by means of a tetrazine ligation/rDA cascade as Warrenner's azabenzonorbornadienes. This new ligation would produce an unprecedented pyrrole-linked protein conjugate. Although Warrenner's chemistry has been broadly exploited for the preparation of isobenzofurans and isoindoles from 7-oxa- and 7-azabenzonorbornadienes, respectively,^[20] to the best of our knowledge no examples have been reported for the tetrazine-mediated preparation of pyrrole derivatives from 7-azanorbornadiene.

Scheme 1. Warrenner's synthesis of isobenzofurans and isoindoles.

The synthesis of racemic [2.2.1]bicyclic bromovinyl sulfone **1** was achieved through Diels–Alder reaction between bromoethynyl *p*-tolyl sulfone and commercial *N*-*tert*-butyloxycarbonyl (Boc)-pyrrole according to a reported procedure (**Scheme S1**).^[21] Bromovinyl sulfone **1** was then reacted with a mixture of protected cysteine and lysine models (*N*-Boc-Cys-OMe and *N*-Boc-Lys-OMe) in a competition experiment in buffer (NaPi, 50 mM, pH 8.0) with dimethylformamide (DMF) as co-solvent. As hypothesized, cysteine reacted rapidly with **1** and the corresponding [2.2.1]bicyclic thiovinyl sulfone **2** was obtained as **unique product** in quantitative yield after 15 min (**Scheme 3**). This reaction was calculated to follow a concerted nucleophilic vinylic substitution (S_NV_o) mechanism with an activation barrier of $\Delta G^\ddagger \approx 12$ kcal mol⁻¹ for *N*-Moc-[2.2.1]azabicyclic bromovinyl sulfone and methyl thiolate abbreviated models (**Figure 1a** and SI for calculations with an *N*-Ac analogue, **Figures S12 and S13**). The reaction with *N*-Boc-Lys-OMe is clearly much slower (as it also happened with the histidine analogue), and no reaction was observed with other amino acid nucleophilic side-chains (see SI for studies of the reactivity of **1** towards different amino acids, **Figures S1-S6**). Accordingly, the reaction between the same *N*-Moc-azabicyclic and methylamine as a lysine model was calculated to be stepwise (i.e. addition, then elimination) and

thousands of times slower with an activation barrier of $\Delta G^\ddagger \approx 16$ kcal mol⁻¹ (**Figure S12**). 7-Azanorbornadiene **2** showed high stability and no rDA reaction was observed after 1 week at 37 °C in CDCl₃.

Scheme 2. Different behaviour of azanorbornadienes type **B** and **D** and their reactions with tetrazines for protein bioconjugation.

7-Azanorbornadiene **2** showed high stability and no rDA reaction was observed after 1 week at 37 °C in CDCl₃, in agreement with the high activation barrier of $\Delta G^\ddagger \approx 28$ kcal mol⁻¹ calculated for an *N*-Ac-azabicyclic analogue in chloroform (SI). This result contrasts with the 7-azanorbornene analogue of type **C**, which we found to be more prone to undergo slow rDA breakdown under the same conditions (calculated activation barrier of $\Delta G^\ddagger \approx 25$ kcal mol⁻¹ in chloroform).^[19] The exceptional reactivity of the bromovinyl sulfone moiety embedded in a [2.2.1]bicyclic skeleton over a less-strained bicyclic system was confirmed through reaction of *N*-Boc-Cys-OMe with differently bridged bicyclic derivatives **3–5**. Compounds **3** and **4**, which feature a [2.2.1]bicyclic skeleton, reacted rapidly with *N*-Boc-Cys-OMe (calculated activation barrier with MeS⁻ of $\Delta G^\ddagger = 11$ and 14 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively, **Figure S13**), whereas less-strained [2.2.2]bicyclic derivative **5** (calculated activation barrier with MeS⁻ of $\Delta G^\ddagger \approx 16$ kcal mol⁻¹, **Figure S13**) did not react under the same conditions. The calculated activation barrier for the reaction of MeS⁻ with *N*-Moc abbreviated model of [2.2.1]azabicyclic bromovinyl ester **6** ($\Delta G^\ddagger \approx 13.8$ kcal mol⁻¹, **Figure S17**) is slightly higher than for the bromovinyl sulfone analogue **1**.

Scheme 3. a. Reactivity of [2.2.1]azabicyclic bromovinyl sulfone **1** towards cysteine/lysine amino acid models. b. Reactivity of other [2.2.1/2]bicyclic bromovinyl sulfones/ester towards a cysteine model.

Figure 1. a. Lowest-energy structures for the a) concerted nucleophilic vinylic substitution (S_NV) of the *N*-acetyl analogue of **1** (*N*-Ac-NBD-Br) with methyl thiolate, b) *retro*-Diels–Alder (*rDA*) of thiovinyl sulfone *N*-Ac-NBD-SMe, c) inverse electron demand Diels–Alder (iEDDA) cycloaddition of *N*-Ac-NBD-SMe with tetrazine DPTz **10**, and d) final *rDA* reaction of the azanorbomadienic sulfone model *N*-Ac-NBD calculated with PCM(H₂O)/M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p). Relative free activation energies (ΔG^\ddagger , in kcal mol⁻¹) are calculated from the corresponding separated reactants. For the calculations on the bromovinyl methyl ester analogue **6**, please see the SI.

Next, we studied the reactivity of the cysteine-conjugated 7-azanorbomadiene **2** towards tetrazines and found that the most electron-rich double bond present in **2** undergoes rapid iEDDA ligation with the electron-deficient 3,6-di-(2-pyridyl)-s-tetrazine (DPTz) **10** under aqueous conditions (Scheme 4). The initial iEDDA was followed by two consecutive *rDA* reactions, which led to the formation of a thiol-conjugated pyrrole **11** in excellent 91% yield after isolation along with pyridazine **12** as a by-product. These observations were corroborated by the much lower activation barrier calculated for the iEDDA reaction between SMe-conjugated 7-azanorbomadiene models and DPTz in water (ΔG^\ddagger = 21–22 kcal mol⁻¹, Figure 1c) with respect to the potentially competitive but unobserved *rDA* decomposition to give the corresponding pyrrole and alkyne products (ΔG^\ddagger ≈ 30 kcal mol⁻¹, Figure 1b). The *rDA* fragmentation from the tricyclic

dihydropyridazine adduct was calculated as fast and thus not rate-limiting (ΔG^\ddagger ≈ 14 kcal mol⁻¹, Figure 1d). Accordingly, the reaction between the tetrazine and **2** was monitored through the decrease in tetrazine absorbance over time. A second-order rate constant (*k*) of 0.026 (±0.002) M⁻¹s⁻¹ at 37 °C was determined for the triple-cascade reaction with the initial cycloaddition step as rate limiting (Figure S7). This value is similar to the one determined for iEDDA ligation between DPTz and azanorbomene of type **C** (Scheme 2).^[19] Similar reaction rates were also reported for iEDDA reactions with aza/oxabenzonorbomadienes.^[17] Finally, [2.2.1]bicyclic analogues **7–9** reacted with DPTz **10** in a similar manner to **2** (Scheme S3).

Scheme 4. Reactivity of thiol-conjugated azanorbomadiene **2** towards tetrazines.

Our data demonstrate that azanorbomadiene bromovinyl sulfones react selectively and rapidly with cysteine, whilst an electron-rich alkene remains unreacted, which enables a further iEDDA-*rDA*-*rDA* reaction cascade to afford a stable pyrrole-linked conjugate at cysteine. The combined advantages of directness, selectivity and further formation of a stable pyrrole linkage by means of iEDDA ligation with tetrazines could allow application of protein and antibody conjugation strategies with the formation of homogenous and stable pyrrole products based simply on these synthetically accessible [2.2.1]bicyclic 2-bromovinyl sulfone reagents. To test this hypothesis, we first decorated **1** with biotin as an affinity probe and model modification (compound **13**, Figure 2, Scheme S4 for synthetic preparation). As a model protein, we chose ubiquitin, which has been engineered with a surface exposed cysteine at position 63 (Ub-K63C).^[22] When we reacted Ub-K63C with 5 equiv. of biotin-functionalized bromovinyl sulfone **13** in NaPi buffer (50 mM, pH 8.0) with DMF as co-solvent (10%) at room temperature for 30 min, a single and homogeneous product was formed as determined by LC-MS (Figure 2a). Further reaction of resulting bioconjugate **14A** with thio-specific Ellman's reagent confirmed that the cysteine was completely consumed during the reaction (Figure S24). To further confirm cysteine chemoselectivity, we first reacted Ub-K63C with a maleimide probe (Figure S28) and then examined reaction of the resulting conjugate with **13**. After incubation of Ub-thiosuccinimide with **13** for 1 h at 25 °C (the conditions required for complete reaction of **13** with Ub-Cys), only < 5% of unspecific reaction, presumably at lysine, was observed (Figure S29). This further corroborates the chemoselectivity of the bicyclic azanorbomadiene bromovinyl sulfone reagents towards cysteine at a protein level.

Once we demonstrated the chemoselectivity of azanorbomadiene bromovinyl sulfone for cysteine-selective protein bioconjugation, we decided to explore if the thio-vinyl

protein conjugates that are stable in both human plasma and in the presence of high amounts of glutathione. The use of azanorbornadiene bromovinyl sulfones for cysteine-selective protein modification combined with azanorbornadiene/tetrazine bond-cleavage reaction, constitutes a new and robust method for the preparation of stable and chemically-defined bioconjugates.

Acknowledgements

We thank the Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport under the FPU program (E.G.M.), the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (CTQ2016-77270-R to A.J.M.-V., E.G.M. and I.R, RTI2018-099592-B-C22 and RYC-2013-14706 to G.J.-O. and RTI2018-099592-B-C21 to F.C.), the EU (Marie-Sklodowska Curie Actions to E.J.M., GA No. 701473) and FCT Portugal (FCT Investigator to G.J.L.B., IF/00624/2015) for funding. We thank Dr André Neves and Prof. Kevin Brindle (CRUK Cambridge Institute, UK) for providing the C2Am protein; Dr S. Massa and Prof N. Devoogdt (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussels) for the generous gift of the HER2-targeting nanobody 2Rb17c, and Dr Vikki Cantrill for her help with the preparation and editing of this manuscript. We also thank CITIUS for NMR and mass spectrometry assistance and BERONIA (Universidad de La Rioja) for computer support. G.J.L.B. is a Royal Society University Research Fellow (URF\R180019).

Keywords: azanorbornadiene • bioorthogonal chemistry • tetrazine • cleavage reactions • inverse electron-demand Diels-Alder

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Stable pyrrole-linked bioconjugates through tetrazine-triggered azanorbornadiene fragmentation

Click to stabilize: An azanorbornadiene bromovinyl sulfone reagent allowed site-selective protein modification and, in combination with a tetrazine partner, enabled the preparation of stable pyrrole-linked protein conjugates through a new bond-cleavage reaction. The latter proceeds through a three-step cascade reaction that involves iEDDA between tetrazine and the azanorbornadiene-tagged protein with subsequent double *retro*-Diels–Alder reaction conjugate.